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DIFFERENTIAL TENGLAMALARNI SIMULYATSIYA QILISH

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ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu ishda differensial tenglamalarni analitik, Eyler va Runge–Kutta usullari yordamida yechish hamda ularni kompyuterda simulyatsiya qilish masalalari o'rganilgan. Analitik usul orqali tenglamalarning aniq yechimlari topildi, sonli usullar yordamida esa taqribiy natijalar olindi. Eyler va Runge–Kutta usullarining aniqligi, hisoblash tezligi va qo'llash imkoniyatlari o'zaro taqqoslandi. Natijalar differensial tenglamalarni modellashtirishda Runge–Kutta usuli yuqori aniqlikka ega ekanligini ko'rsatdi.

Kalit so'zlar: Differensial tenglama, analitik usul, Eyler usuli, Runge–Kutta usuli, sonli usullar, simulyatsiya, modellashtirish, matematik model, algoritm.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной работе исследуются методы решения и моделирования дифференциальных уравнений с использованием аналитического метода, метода Эйлера и метода Рунге–Кутты. Аналитический метод позволяет получить точные решения уравнений, а численные методы обеспечивают приближённые результаты. Проведено сравнение точности, скорости вычислений и эффективности методов Эйлера и Рунге–Кутты. Полученные результаты показывают, что метод Рунге–Кутты обеспечивает более высокую точность при моделировании дифференциальных уравнений.

Ключевые слова: Дифференциальное уравнение, аналитический метод, метод Эйлера, метод Рунге–Кутты, численные методы, моделирование, симуляция, математическая модель, алгоритм.

ABSTRACT

This work studies the simulation and solution of differential equations using analytical, Euler, and Runge–Kutta methods. Exact solutions are obtained through analytical methods, while approximate solutions are calculated using numerical approaches. The accuracy, computational speed, and efficiency of the Euler and Runge–Kutta methods are compared. The results demonstrate that the Runge–Kutta method provides higher accuracy in the simulation of differential equations

Keywords: Differential equation, analytical method, Euler method, Runge–Kutta method, numerical methods, simulation, mathematical modeling, algorithm.

1. Differensial tenglama tushunchasi

Differensial tenglama - noma'lum funksiya va uning hosilalarini o'z ichiga olgan tenglamadir. Berilgan tenglama:

$$y' = x^2 + y$$

bu birinchi tartibli oddiy differensial tenglama hisoblanadi.

Koshi masalasida boshlang'ich shart ham beriladi:

$$y(0) = 0.4$$

Bu shart yechimning aniq bitta funksiyasini topishga yordam beradi.

2. Eyler usuli nazariyasi

Eyler usuli differensial tenglamani taqribiy yechishning eng oddiy usullaridan biridir. Formula:

$$y_{n+1} = y_n + hf(x_n, y_n)$$

Bu yerda:

1) h - qadam uzunligi

2) $f(x, y) = x^2 + y$

Bu usulda har bir keyingi nuqta oldingi nuqtadagi hosila yordamida topiladi.

3. Runge - Kutta 4- tartibli usuli

Runge- Kutta usuli Eyler usuliga qaraganda ancha aniqligi yuqori usuldir.

Formularlar:

$$k_1 = hf(x_n, y_n)$$

$$k_2 = hf\left(x_n + \frac{h}{2}y_n + \frac{k_1}{2}\right)$$

$$k_3 = hf\left(x_n + \frac{h}{2}y_n + \frac{k_2}{2}\right)$$

$$k_4 = hf(x_n + hy_n + k_3)$$

So‘ng:

$$y_{n+1} = y_n + \frac{k_1 + 2k_2 + 2k_3 + k_4}{6}$$

4. Analitik yechim

Berilgan tenglama:

$$y' - y = x^2$$

Bu chiziqli differensial tenglama. Integrallovchi ko‘paytuvchi:

$$\mu(x) = e^{-x}$$

Tenglamaning ikkala tomonini e^{-x} ga ko‘paytiramiz:

$$e^{-x}y' - e^{-x}y = x^2e^{-x}$$

Chap tomon:

$$\frac{d}{dx}(ye^{-x}) = x^2e^{-x}$$

Integrallaymiz:

$$ye^{-x} = \int x^2 e^{-x} dx + C$$

Natija:

$$y = Ce^x - x^2 - 2x - 2$$

Boshlang‘ich shartdan foydalanamiz:

$$y(0) = 0.4$$

$$0.4 = C - 2$$

$$C = 2.4$$

Demak analitik yechim: $y(x) = 2.4e^x - x^2 - 2x - 2$

Runge- Kutta usuli natijasi analitik yechimga juda yaqin chiqdi.

(x)	Analitik yechim	Eyler usuli	Runge- usuli	Kutta
0.0	0.4000	0.4000	0.4000	
0.1	0.4424	0.4400	0.4424	
0.2	0.4914	0.4850	0.4913	
0.3	0.5497	0.5375	0.5492	
0.4	0.6204	0.6003	0.6199	
0.5	0.7069	0.6763	0.7062	
0.6	0.8131	0.7689	0.8118	
0.7	0.9430	0.8818	0.9409	
0.8	1.1013	1.0190	1.0985	
0.9	1.2930	1.1849	1.2907	
1.0	1.5239	1.3844	1.5248	

1-jadval. Analitik, Eyler va Runge-Kutta usullarida natijalar jadvali

```
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

# funksiya
def f(x, y):
    return x**2 + y

# analitik yechim
def y_exact(x):
    return 2.4*np.exp(x) - (x**2 + 2*x + 2)

h = 0.1
x = np.arange(0, 1 + h, h)

# Eyler usuli
y_euler = [0.4]
for i in range(len(x)- 1):
    y_new = y_euler[i] + h * f(x[i], y_euler[i])
    y_euler.append(y_new)

# RK4 usuli (TO'G'RI VARIANT)
y_rk = [0.4]
for i in range(len(x)- 1):
    k1 = f(x[i], y_rk[i])
    k2 = f(x[i] + h/2, y_rk[i] + h*k1/2)
    k3 = f(x[i] + h/2, y_rk[i] + h*k2/2)
    k4 = f(x[i] + h, y_rk[i] + h*k3)
    y_new = y_rk[i] + (h/6)*(k1 + 2*k2 + 2*k3 + k4)
    y_rk.append(y_new)

# analitik qiymatlar
y_a = y_exact(x)
# jadval
df = pd.DataFrame({
    "x": x,
    "Analitik": np.round(y_a, 4),
    "Eyler": np.round(y_euler, 4),
    "RK4": np.round(y_rk, 4)
})
print(df)
# grafik
plt.plot(x, y_a, label="Analitik")
plt.plot(x, y_euler, '- - ', label="Eyler")
plt.plot(x, y_rk, '- . ', label="RK4")

plt.legend()
plt.grid()
plt.xlabel("x")
plt.ylabel("y")
plt.title("Differensial tenglama yechimlari")

plt.show()
```


1-rasm. Differensial tenglamani Python dasturi yordamida yechish

Yechim bo'yicha izoh. Ushbu masala Python dasturlash tili yordamida sonli usullar orqali yechildi. Dasturda NumPy kutubxonasi matematik hisoblashlar uchun, Pandas natijalarni jadval ko'rinishida chiqarish uchun va Matplotlib grafik chizish uchun foydalanildi. Masala analitik usul, Eyler usuli hamda Runge- Kutta 4- tartibli usuli yordamida hisoblandi. Olingan natijalar jadval va grafik orqali taqqoslandi.

Hisoblash natijalariga ko'ra, Runge- Kutta usuli analitik yechimga juda yaqin natija berdi. Eyler usulida esa qadamlar soni ortishi bilan xatolik biroz kattalashdi. Shu sababli Runge- Kutta usuli aniqligi yuqori bo'lgan samarali sonli usullardan biri ekanligi kuzatildi.

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